

Whorl maggot rating

Whorl maggot rating taken weekly on plots of IR36 treated with different insecticides. IRRI, 1979 dry season. 1 = 0-1 leaf damaged/hill; 3 = 2 or more but less than 1/3 of leaves damaged; 5 = 1/3 to 1/2 of leaves damaged; 7 = more than 1/2 of leaves damaged with no leaf breaking; 9 = more than 1/2 of leaves damaged with some leaves broken.

the most effective treatment for whorl maggot control. Control was also satisfactory on plots sprayed twice with monocrotophos, fensulfathion,

triazophos, or azinphos ethyl. Carbofuran as a paddy water broadcast treatment initially gave good

control, but its residual activity was shorter than when it was incorporated into the soil. ■

Residues of carbofuran in soil, rice grain, and straw as affected by rates and number of applications

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Insecticides with greater persistence leave more toxic residues on treated crops and become a health hazard for men and cattle. Carbofuran is effective against many major rice pests, but its residues status in the grain, straw, and soil after

paddy harvest is not known.

Carbofuran granules at 1.0 kg a.i./ha were broadcast 1 to 3 times at different stages of crop growth in nonreplicated micro field plots planted with Jaya spaced 20 x 20 cm. The treatments were 1 application at 15, 40, or 70 days after transplanting (DT), 1 application at 15 and 40 DT, 1 application at 70 DT, and an untreated check (see table).

At or after harvest, samples of soil, grain, and straw from 12 random plants and 100 g of grain randomly

drawn from each treatment were collected and were analyzed by the gas chromatographic technique. The residues in grain of treated plots ranged from 0.034 to 0.056 ppm; residues in the straw ranged from 0.039 to 0.112 ppm. The soil contained higher residues — 0.261 to 0.672 ppm. The residue tolerances established for carbofuran in the USA were 1.0 ppm for rice straw and 0.2 ppm for rice grain. The carbofuran residues in this study were within those prescribed tolerance limits. ■

Carbofuran residues in rice grain, straw, and soil of the variety Jaya, summer, 1977.

Treatment ^a	Total dosage (kg a.i./ha)	Time lag (days) between last treatment and		Residues (ppm) of carbofuran		
		Harvest	Residue analysis	Grain	Straw	Soil
1 application Furadan 3G at 15 DT	1.0	98	122	0.034	0.051	0.261
2 applications Furadan 3G at 15 and 40 DT	2.0	78	102	0.044	0.051	0.288
3 applications Furadan 3G at 15, 40, and 70 DT	3.0	48	72	0.056	0.112	0.345
1 application Furadan 3G at 40 DT	1.0	78	102	0.041	0.048	0.315
1 application Furadan 3G at 70 DT	1.0	48	72	0.038	0.039	0.672
Control	-	-	-	0.002	0.007	0.034

^aDT = days after transplanting.